

Extraction of Molybdenum with a Liquid Anion-exchanger and its Application in Plant Samples

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Manuscript received 13 July 1988, accepted 30 March 1990

Molybdenum has been selectively and quantitatively extracted as $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{tartarate})_2]^{2-}$ with Aliquat 336 in 1-butanol medium. Extraction conditions, separation from various ions and nature of the extracted species are described. The method has been applied for the separation of trace molybdenum in plant samples followed by its atomic absorption spectrophotometric determination.

MOLYBDENUM is accumulated by leguminous plants and the important role played by this metal is in the process of symbiotic fixation of atmospheric nitrogen. A relationship can be observed between the metabolism of nutrient-accumulating plants and their capacity to accumulate inorganic nutrients¹. Flame atomic absorption spectrophotometric (AAS) methods for determination of molybdenum has been reported by several authors². As the effects of various ions on the atomic absorption signals of molybdenum have shown that a number of ions interfere³, it may be necessary to further elaborate the process by an extraction stage. High molecular weight amines have been used for the extraction of different metals as anionic complexes⁴. The tartarate complex of molybdenum was studied by the batch equilibrium method on Dowex 2X-8 anion-exchange resin⁵. The present communication reports the extraction behaviour of molybdenum as $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{tartarate})_2]^{2-}$ with liquid anion-exchanger, Aliquat 336 in 1-butanol. High temperature flame AAS has been used in the present method for the determination of trace molybdenum in plant samples after its extraction with Aliquat 336.

Experimental

Aliquat 336 (Fluka, A.G.) liquid anion-exchanger was used as such. The stock solution of molybdenum was prepared by dissolving ammonium molybdate (E. Marck, F.R.G.) and the solution was standardised gravimetrically as molybdyl oxinate⁶. All other reagents used were of analytical reagent grade.

A Shimadzu AA-646 atomic absorption spectrophotometer was used. The operating conditions maintained for molybdenum were as follows: Mo hollow cathode lamp current, 9 mA; wavelength, 313.3 nm; slit-width, 0.38 nm; burner height, 11 mm; acetylene flow rate, 8 dm³ min⁻¹; nitrous oxide flow rate, 7 dm³ min⁻¹. The pH

values were measured with a Sambros 335 digital pH-meter.

General procedure: To an aliquot of the stock solution containing 450 µg of molybdenum, an excess of tartarate solution was added, pH adjusted to ~2.2, and then phthalate buffer solution (2 ml; pH 2.2) was added. The resulting solution was shaken for 5 min with a solution (10 ml) of 5% Aliquat 336 dissolved in 1-butanol, when two layers were separated. The aqueous phase was discarded and from the organic phase the metal ion was back-extracted with 0.1 M HClO₄ solution (2 × 4 ml). The combined aqueous phase was equilibrated with 1-butanol (5 ml) to remove any trace of exchanger and the aqueous phase was taken in a 10 ml volumetric flask. Then Al^{III} solution (1 ml) containing 10000 µg was added to it and the volume made up to the mark with double-distilled water. The solution was then aspirated into AAS and the absorbance was measured against blank. Molybdenum concentration was determined a reagent from the calibration curve.

Preparation of plant sample solutions: Each of the plant sample was oven-dried, pulverised, placed in a desiccator and treated in the following way⁷. The plant sample (3–8 g) was mixed with ethanol (1 ml), ignited over a low flame and finally placed in a muffle furnace (700–800°) for 20–30 min until it was ash. The residue was treated with dilute NaOH solution and placed on a water-bath for about 5 min, filtered and washed with dilute tartarate solution. The filtrate was made up to 25 ml with double-distilled water. An aliquot was taken and molybdenum was determined after adding excess tartarate solution, adjusting the pH to 2.2 and using general procedure.

Results and Discussion

Optimisation of different parameters: Extraction of molybdenum-tartarate complex was quantitative in the pH range 1.8–2.5. The working pH

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF MOLYBDENUM IN DIFFERENT PLANT SAMPLES

Sample	Amount taken g	Molybdenum found* ($\mu\text{g g}^{-1}$)		
		Direct AAS	Present method	Spectro-photometric method
<i>Lens esculenta</i> Moench.	4.003 00	6.21	4.13	4.19
<i>Dolichos lablab</i> Linn.	5.730 70	12.21	8.26	8.32
<i>Phaseolus mungo</i> Linn.	6.776 45	8.31	6.11	6.21
<i>Dolichos biflorus</i> Linn.				
(i) Stems	4.859 45	10.55	8.52	8.65
(ii) Leaves	7.965 16	6.32	4.11	4.23
<i>Lathyrus sativus</i>	3.783 14	7.90	6.37	6.40

*Average of 3 determinations.

was 2.2 and phthalate buffer was used to maintain the pH. The extraction behaviour of the metal complex was studied from aqueous solution at the working pH into various organic solvents containing Aliquat 336. The results indicate that the complex was quantitatively extractable into 1-butanol, the percentage of extraction being 100. The extraction with other solvents shows 86.9% in benzene and 75.9% in amyl alcohol. With chloroform, isobutyl methyl ketone, toluene and cyclohexane, emulsion was formed. The extraction was completed within 5 min and stripping was completed within 1 min. However, in both the cases, it was kept for 5 min to settle the equilibrium.

Separation of molybdenum: Separation of molybdenum (45 μg) was carried out in presence of various ion within an error of $\pm 2\%$. The results are as follows: Na^+ , NH_4^+ , Cl^- , NO_3^- , ClO_4^- , SO_4^{2-} (10000 μg each); VO_5^- , SCN^- (1000 μg each); Fe^{3+} , Mn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , WO_4^{2-} , Br^- , H_2PO_4^- (500 μg each); Ba^{2+} , Sr^{2+} , Ca^{2+} (400 μg each).

The separation of molybdenum (45 μg) was possible in the presence of more than one foreign ion in the following mixtures (within an error of not more than $\pm 2\%$): Fe^{3+} (300 μg) + Mg^{2+} (400 μg); WO_4^{2-} (300 μg) + Zn^{2+} (400 μg); Cd^{2+} (200 μg) + Ca^{2+} (300 μg); Ni^{2+} (400 μg) + Ba^{2+} (300 μg) + SCN^- (400 μg); VO_5^- (800 μg) + Br^- (300 μg) + Co^{2+} (400 μg).

Application: Amount of molybdenum in plant samples was determined by AAS in an aliquot of the sample solution after separation of the metal by the general procedure (Table 1). Direct AAS always gives higher values due to matrix effects. The results obtained by the present method are comparable to the values found by the spectrophotometric method⁷.

Nature of the extracted species: The uncomplexed Mo^{VI} species in the more acidic solution exists as MoO_2^{2+} ion⁸. So the tartarate complex may be represented as $[\text{MoO}_2(\text{tartarate})_2]^{2-}$. Similar complexes have been reported in the literature⁹.

The extraction of the complex is quantitative provided the Aliquat 336- $\text{MoO}_2(\text{tartarate})_2^{2-}$ mole-ratio is ≥ 2 . Plot of $\log D$ vs $\log[\text{Aliquat 336}]$ provides a straight line with a slope value of ~ 2 . Thus the simple extraction mechanism may be represented as

where o is organic phase, a the aqueous phase and R_4N^+ is Aliquat 336.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (S.B.) is grateful to the Head of the Department of Chemistry for facilities.

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